

Heterocyclic Systems. Part I. Synthesis of Selected Bis-benzimidazoles*

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A few representative members of a series of bis-benzimidazole derivatives have been prepared and purified.

The chemistry of benzimidazole derivatives encompasses a wide field of interest ranging from vitamin B₁₂¹, yeast antimetabolite², high polymers³ to organic semi- and photo-conductors.⁴ This unique ring system is structurally related to the biologically important purines and possesses interesting absorption and emission characteristics and photoconductive properties. As part of studies of energy-transfer properties of organic heterocyclic systems, we have investigated the synthesis and electrical properties of a series of bis-benzimidazole derivatives. In the present report, the preparation and purification of few representative members of this series of compounds are discussed.

The 2-substituted benzimidazoles are usually obtained by the condensation of aromatic *ortho*-diamines with aliphatic or aromatic carboxylic acids in acid solution following the classical method of Phillips.⁵ The extension of this method to 2,2'-bis-benzimidazoles was made by Shriner and Upson.⁶ The use of polyphosphoric acid as a condensing agent for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzimidazoles and thiazoles was first reported by Hein *et al*.⁷ and was subsequently extended to 2-substituted purines by Fu *et al*.⁸ Further extension of polyphosphoric acid method was accomplished by Wang and Jullie⁹ for 2,2'-bis-benzimidazole with aliphatic connecting bridges, and by Nyilas and Pinter¹⁰ for the corresponding 2, 2'-bis-benzoxazoles and thiazoles.

In the present study polyphosphoric acid was used whenever possible. Much cleaner products were, however, isolated when anhydrous phenol was used as condensing agent, specifically with 2, 2'-bis-benzimidazole derivatives with aliphatic connecting bridges.

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2. Woolley, *J. Biol. Chem.* 1944, 152, 225.

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4. Aftergut and Brown, "Electronic Properties of Organic Compounds" in *Organic Semiconductors*, Ed. Brophy and Buttrey, D. MacMillan Co., New York, 1962, p. 79.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2399

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2277.

7. *Ibid.*, 1957, 79, 427.

8. *J. Org. Chem.* 1965, 30, 1916.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 5706.

10. *Ibid.*, 1960, 82, 609.

The electronic spectra of bis-benzimidazoles show a consistent pattern of triplets in the ultraviolet region, shifting to higher wave lengths with the extension of conjugation. The IR spectra were taken in KBr pellets and all showed absorptions near 3μ (CH), 6.01μ (C=N), 6.25μ (C=C), and 6.75μ (aromatic) regions, and are entirely consistent with the assigned structures.

EXPERIMENTAL*

The UV and IR spectra were taken in Cary Model 14 and Perkin Elmer-Infracord recording spectrophotometers. UV spectra were taken in ethanol, unless otherwise mentioned. Elemental analyses were performed by Galbraith Laboratories, Knoxville, Tenn.

Polyphosphoric Method (Method A).—A mixture of 2 moles of aromatic *ortho*-diamine and 1 mole of dibasic acid or di-ester in approximately 30-50 ml. of polyphosphoric acid was heated in an oil bath with mechanical stirring under a nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction temperature (internal) was maintained at 120-140° for 1 hr. and then at 150-180° for 4-5 hr. After cooling, the dark reaction mixture was poured on ice and the product isolated after neutralisation to pH 7.5 with sodium hydroxide. The precipitated bis-benzimidazole derivative filtered, washed with water, followed by ethanol, and crystallised.

Anhydrous Phenol Method (Method B).—In place of polyphosphoric acid as condensing agent (Method A), the reactants were added to anhydrous phenol (20-50 g.) and the mixture was heated under nitrogen atmosphere at 130-200° for 2½-5 hr. The reaction mixture, after cooling, was extracted with light petroleum and the solid residue was washed with water and with ethanol; it was dried and crystallised.

(a) *1,2-Bis-(2,2'-benzimidazolyl) ethane*¹¹ (Method B).—*o*-Phenylenediamine (0.05M, 5.4 g.) and 4.3 g. (0.025 mole) diethyl succinate (0.025M, 4.3 g.) provided 2.3g(35%) of the product, m.p. 4.06-4.09° (DMF). (Found: C, 73.28; H, 5.58; N, 21.21. C₁₆H₁₄N₄ requires C, 73.26; H, 5.36; N, 21.36%). λ_{max} at 243 m μ (ϵ , 13,000), 247 m μ (ϵ , 12,500), 274 m μ (ϵ , 16,800), 282 m μ (ϵ , 21,700).

(b) *1,2-Bis-(2,2'-benzimidazolyl) ethane*¹² (Method A).—From a mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.05M, 5.4 g.) and of diethyl maleate (0.025M, 4.3 g.) a yield of 6.0 g. (93%) of the product was obtained, m.p. 426-27°. (Found: C, 73.58; H, 4.79; N, 21.33. C₁₆H₁₄N₄ requires C, 73.82; H, 4.65; N, 21.53%). λ_{max} at 347 m μ (ϵ , 36,400), 362 m μ (ϵ , 43,900), 381 m μ (ϵ , 29,800).

(c) *4,4'-Bis-(2,2'-benzimidazolyl) biphenyl* (Method A).—*o*-Phenylenediamine (0.05M, 5.4 g.) and biphenyl-4, 4'-dicarboxylic acid (0.025M, 6.06 g.) furnished 7.0g. (72%) of the product, m.p. >495°, which was purified by high vacuum sublimation. (Found: C, 80.72; H, 4.50; N, 14.43. C₂₆H₁₈N₄ requires C, 80.80; H, 4.70; N, 14.50%) λ_{max} (DMF) at 345 m μ (ϵ 71,000).

*Melting points are uncorrected, and were taken with a Mel-temp. melting point apparatus.

11. Ref. 6 reports m.p. 325-30° for material prepared by the method described in Ref. 5.

12. Ackeman and Meyer, U.S.P. 2515 173 (CA 45,666) by oxidation of (a) to (b), B.P. 600 696 (CA 42, 7342).

(d) 4,4'-Bis(Naphtha-(2,3-d)-imidazolyl)biphenyl (Method A). 3.96g (0.025 mole) of 2,3-diaminophthalene (0.025M, 3.96 g.) and of biphenyl-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid (0.012M, 3.03g.) provided 6.0 gm (90%) of the product, m.p. >490° (DMF). (Found: C, 83.75; H, 4.39; N, 11.42. C₂₄H₁₂N₄ requires C, 83.92; H, 4.56; N, 11.52%). λ_{max} (in DMF) at 363 m μ (ϵ , 84,700) and 303 m μ (ϵ , 54,100).

(e) 2,2'-Bis-(2,3-pyridoimidazolyl) ethane (Method B). 2,3-diaminopyridine (0.009M, 1.0g. and 8 ml. of diethyl succinate (8 ml.) furnished 300 mg. (27%) of the product, m.p. >400° (dil. acetic acid). (Found: C, 63.75; H, 4.70; N, 31.88. C₁₄H₁₁N₆ requires C, 63.82; H, 4.58; N, 31.80%). λ_{max} at 244 m μ (ϵ , 8,500), 284 m μ (ϵ , 27,500), 287 m μ (ϵ , 29,800) 293 m μ (ϵ , 26,300).

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